

Models and Methods: the reality check by the regulatory science community in a world of change

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Abstract

The first guidance on Good Cell Culture Practice (GCCP) dates back to 2005 (Coecke et al. 2005). With the availability of human-induced pluripotent (2006) stem cells, the potential applications of human cell culture models have been greatly broadened. When using stem cells and stem-cell-derived models in research, product development, testing, and manufacture of biotechnology products and cell-based medicines, it remains critical to include aspects of quality assurance. As such, the original set of GCCP principles of best practice can be used as a basis to assure good cell and tissue practices and conditions when working with stem cell-derived test systems in simple set-ups or in very technologically advanced formats (Pamies et al., 2017). GCCP and its next-generation principles (GCCP 2.0) are intended as guidance to obtain reliable and relevant study data. Applying GCCP as part of overall Good In Vitro Method Practices (GIVIMP, OECD 2018) by the global life science community is leading to more harmonisation of in vitro method-related processes and procedures. Researchers are key players to ensure the use of such best scientific and quality practices and are ideal ambassadors to use them in the novel generation of stem cell and tissue-based methods. The European Commission Joint Research Centre's European Union Reference Laboratory for Alternatives to Animal Testing (EURL ECVAM) is working on developing and validating innovative, mechanistic methods and approaches based on current harmonized scientific and quality standards complying with the GCCP principles and the GIVIMP guidance document (OECD, 2018) and is crowd-sourcing for introducing stem cells and stem-cell-derived methods into the required regulatory test batteries for identifying thyroid disrupting chemicals. Key instruments to disseminate globally harmonized good cell, tissue, and method practices are published principles and guidance, conferences, face-to-face meetings, training, webinars, templates (Krebs et al., 2019), reporting, and evaluation tools (e.g. <http://www.scirap.org/>) and e-learning training materials.

References

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